

THE PRESENT AND FUTURE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR AERONAUTICAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Advanced composites, featuring continuous reinforcing fibres in polymer matrices, have demonstrated their ability to provide reliable, weight-saving structures for various aeronautical applications. It is no longer a question of whether advanced composites will be used in future, but rather how to apply them more cost-effectively. It has become obvious that early expectations as to producing composite structures at a cost level comparable to metallic parts have in most cases not been met, despite proven significant advances in cost-cutting.

Starting from a review of composite structures that have been realised for aeronautical applications, the paper will focus on new developments in the area of composite technologies and their impact on the future use of composites in aerospace. Topics which will be addressed include

- new thermoset resins
- thermoplastics
- textile processes for the production of complex fibre preforms
- resin impregnation processes (i.e. RTM, pultrusion)
- "smart composites"
- recycling

Although all these developments will promote the continuing growth of composite applications, the timing for significant breakthroughs with an all-composite wing and ultimately an all-composite fuselage in large commercial aircraft is still impossible to predict.